

Supplementary data

Table S1 shows culture-dependent isolates of the four raw milk cheeses in comparison to culture-independent analysis (Fig.1)

Cheeses	Isolate species based on culture-dependent 16S rRNA sequencing
Brie 2	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> (1) <i>Hafnia paralvei</i> (3) <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> (3)
Camembert 2	<i>Levilactobacillus brevis</i> (1) <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> (2) <i>Hafnia paralvei</i> (2) <i>Enterobacteriaceae bacterium</i> (1)
Reblochon	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> (1) <i>Leuconstoc mesenteroides</i> (2) <i>Hafnia alvei</i> (2) <i>Hafnia paralvei</i> (2)
Smoked Drumlin	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> (1) <i>Staphylococcus casei</i> (1) <i>Staphylococcus equorum</i> (2)

Table S2: Viable counts on LM17 agar from the eight additional cheeses for LAB species analysis

Cheese	42 °C (cfu/ml)
Fleur du Maquis	7.9×10^5
Brie	2.90×10^5
Saint Felicien	2.87×10^5
Mozzarella	1.3×10^5
Caciocavallo	2.72×10^5
Camembert	3.00×10^5
Pecorino 1	2.98×10^5
Pecorino 2	1.46×10^5

A

B

Figure S1: shows results from microscopic evaluation of *Hafnia* cells, A-strain CO3 grown on LM17 agar, B-strain CO1 grown on LB agar.

	<i>Lactobacillus casei</i>	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus paracasei</i>	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	<i>Levilactobacillus brevis</i>	<i>Pediococcus acidilactici</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	<i>Enterococcus durans</i>	<i>Hafnia paralvei</i>
Brie							1		1	2
Camembert	1									1
Pecorino 1							1	1		
Pecorino 2								2		
Saint Felicien		1				1			1	
Mozzerella			1	1						
Caciocavallo		1		1						
Fleur du Maquis		4								

Figure S2: Species identification of the 22 isolates from eight cheeses based on 16SrRNA gene sequencing. The number of isolates per cheese is colour-coded as per the legend.

Figure S3: Comparison based on culture-dependent and culture-independent analysis of the 12 analysed cheeses. While metagenomics analysis identifies more species than culture-dependent analysis, dominant species are comparable in both methods.

Figure S4: *Hafnia* temperature growth profiles in LM17 and LB broth after 24 hours incubation

Figure S5: colony morphology of representative *Hafnia* strains CO2 and CO3 on LM17 agar

Figure S6: Shows *Hafnia* gas production in LM17 broth after 24 hours of incubation.

Figure S7: All ten *H. paralvei* species metabolize lactose. Their colonies turned pink whereas *H. alvei* species remained yellow, indicating they do not use lactose.